

Kinetic Parameters of Thermal Dehydration and Decomposition from Thermoanalytical Curves of Zinc *dl*-Lactate

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Zinc *dl*-lactate trihydrate undergoes dehydration followed by single step decomposition to ZnO when heated at the rate of 1/6 K s⁻¹ in air. Kinetic parameters of the two steps have been approximated employing Freeman-Carroll, Horowitz-Metzger, Coats-Redfern, Fuoss, Karkhanavala-Dharwadkar and Zsako methods. The latter four methods furnished more consistent values. Both the steps follow Avrami-Erofeev laws.

The thermal decomposition of metal carboxylates has attracted many workers^{1,2} but no systematic attempt has been made to study the kinetic and mechanistic parameters of thermal decomposition of lactate trihydrate. Such a study acquires significance in the light of the fact that lactate ion as well as the zinc ion are among the important constituents of many foodstuff which are subjected to heating during cooking. This significance and its theoretical importance prompted us to analyze the thermogravimetric data of the title compound for the kinetic and mechanistic models of dehydration and decomposition.

Results and Discussion

The decomposition was found to be taking place in two steps, the first being dehydration. The end-product was analyzed for ZnO which is common with most of the zinc salts^{2,3}.

The α - T plots of both the steps show that there is no induction period. There is no evidence of physical desorption, nucleation or branching⁴. The thermoanalytical data were processed for the search of the most likely mechanism of decomposition.

The TG data on the steps were analyzed for the kinetic parameters using the different difference-differential, differential and integral methods of Freeman-Carroll, Horowitz-Metzger, Coats-Redfern, Fuoss-Salyer-Wilson, Karkhanavala-Dharwadkar and Zsako^{5,6} (eqns. 1-7) Figs. 1-4. Freeman-Carroll :

$$\frac{(E/2.303R)\Delta T^{-1}}{-b + [\Delta \log (dW/dt)]/\Delta \log W_r} = \quad (1)$$

Horowitz-Metzger :

$$\ln \ln (w_c/W_r) = E\theta/RT_s^2 \quad (2)$$

Coats-Redfern :

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{(for } b = 1), \\ & \log [-\log \{(1-\alpha)/T^2\}] = \\ & \quad \{\log (AR/qE)\}[1-2RT/E]-E/2.303RT \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

(for $b \neq 1$)

$$\log \left[\frac{\{(1-(1-\alpha)^{1-b})\}/\{T^2(1-b)\}}{\{\log (AR/qE)\}[1-2RT/E]-E/2.303RT} \right] = \quad (4)$$

Fuoss/Karkhanavala :

$$E = [RT_i^2/W_i] (dW/dT)_i \quad (5)$$

Zsako :

$$\log (AE/Rq) = \log g(\alpha) - \log p(x) = B \quad (6)$$

$$\log A = \bar{B} + \log Rq - \log E \quad (7)$$

where E is the activation energy, A the collision frequency, b the order of reaction, $W_r = w_c - W$ (w_c = weight-loss at completion of reaction, W = total weight-loss upto time t), R the gas constant, T the absolute temperature, T_s the reference temperature such that at T_s , $1W/W_0 = 1/e$, $\theta = T - T_s$, α the conversion degree, $F(\alpha)$ the conversion integral, q the heating rate, T_i the temperature of inflection, W_i the weight at T_i , $(dW/dT)_i$ the slope at the point of inflection and \bar{B} is the A.M. of the most consistent series of B -values as obtained from eqn. (6).

In Freeman-Carroll method, a straight-line plot of $\Delta T^{-1}/\Delta \log W_r$ versus $\Delta \log (dW/dt)/\Delta \log W_r$ furnished the value of order of reaction from the intercept and the value of activation energy from the slope ($E/2.303R$). Similarly, the Horowitz-Metzger plot of $\ln \ln w_c/W_r$ against θ is a straight line whose slope is E/RT_s^2 . The graphical Coats-Redfern method involved search of the most 'straight-line' curve between $\log \left[\frac{1-(1-\alpha)^{1-b}}{T^2(1-b)} \right]$ or $\log \left[\frac{-\log (1-\alpha)}{T^2} \right]$ (where $b = 1$) versus $1/T$. The most 'straight-line' gave the suitability of the order of reaction assumed in the calculation and also the value of activation energy from the slope ($-E/2.303R$). In Fuoss method, the point of inflection was directly taken from the TG trace, and in K-D method, it was obtained from a modified thermogram which was plotted as α versus $(T_0 + \theta)$ (where T_0 is the inception temperature and θ the percent of the total span of temperature covered for a given value of α). The Zsako method involved calculations of various $\log g(\alpha)$ values corresponding to different points at intervals of 10° and assuming different values of $g(\alpha)$. The $\log p(x)$ values corresponding to different E and T values, were taken from the Zsako Table⁶. The B and E

Fig. 1. Freeman-Carroll, Horowitz-Metzger and Karkhanavala-Dharwadkar plots for the first step decomposition of zinc *dl*-lactate.

Fig. 2. Coats-Redfern plots for the first step decomposition of zinc *dl*-lactate.

values which furnished the lowest value of standard deviation δ_{\min} in a series of B values, were taken as the best ones. Final E and B values were obtained through extrapolation technique involving search of minima in $(\delta_{\min}-E)$ and $(\delta_{\min}-B)$ plots. The arithmetic mean of the most consistent B values, \bar{B} thus obtained, was used for the calculation of A values. The A value was utilized for the approximation of the value of entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) through the thermodynamic equation (eqn. 7),

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = R \ln Ah / kT_{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where $T_{1/2}$ is the temperature at which half of the conversion is complete. The A value acquires significance in the Arrhenius equation.

All these methods are based on the adoption of the principles of homogeneous gas or liquid phase kinetics into solid phase reactions with minor variations or modifications⁸. These assumptions hold good and the kinetic parameters acquire significance if the particle size and the sample size are kept small⁸.

The values of order of reaction, activation energy, col-

Fig. 3. Freeman-Carroll, Horowitz-Metzger and Karkhanavala-Dharwadkar plots for the second step decomposition of zinc *dl*-lactate.

Fig. 4. Coats-Redfern plots for the second step decomposition of zinc *dl*-lactate.

lision frequency and activation entropy for the dehydration and decomposition as obtained by different methods are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—KINETIC PARAMETERS OF THERMAL DEHYDRATION OF ZINC *dl*-LACTATE TRIHYDRATE*

Parameter	F-C	H-M	C-R	Fuoss	K-D	Zsako
Step-I:						
E	49.86	70.44	67.39	46.27	45.59	52.64
A	7.1×10^5	2.5×10^2	5.14×10^6	5.67×10^3	3.37×10^4	1.5×10^4
ΔS^\ddagger	-135.42	-201.51	-118.97	-175.58	-179.80	-167.49
b	1.25	1/3	1	-	-	0
Step-II:						
E	104.24	81.73	65.63	55.71	58.79	66.10
A	1×10^{10}	9.65×10^2	2.28×10^3	4.07×10^2	5.57×10^3	1.32×10^3
ΔS^\ddagger	-60.12	-195.45	-187.28	-201.62	-179.80	-191.80
b	0.8	0.15	1	-	-	1

* E is in kJ mol^{-1} , A in s^{-1} , ΔS^\ddagger in $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$.

The value of activation entropy of both the steps suggest appreciable rearrangement among various degrees of freedom leading to a more ordered structure of the transition states.

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